
Barriers to Accessing Legal Information by Women of Malava Sub-County, Kakamega, Kenya

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ABSTRACT

Rationale of study: This study was conducted at a very pivotal time in the history of Kenya where the values and principles of equity, social justice, equality, human rights, human dignity just to mention a few are exalted in the constitution. The choice to focus on women was informed by the principle of social justice and equity that lay focus on marginalized groups of persons. Accessible legal information is very essential in enabling people access their legal rights and conversely the opposite is also true. The study endeavoured to establish the barriers that challenge women of Malava sub county from accessing and using legal information, a scenario that excludes them from social justice.

Methodology: The intention of this investigation was not to generalize from the sample but rather to describe and explain the barriers that hinder women from accessing legal information. This study was thus qualitative and the justification for this approach was that the subject of legal information has not been adequately addressed in the context of social justice with respect to women of Malava sub county, Kakamega. This section probed respondents on the challenges they felt hindered them from accessing legal information.

Findings: The findings from the respondents which were captured verbatim demonstrate the expressions, emotions and thoughts that emanated from how they experienced and felt the barriers hindered them from accessing and using legal information.

Implications: This study established that the barriers women of Malava sub county faced in securing legal information subject them to information injustice. This is contrary to the country's principle of equity, human rights, equality, inclusivity and social justice as enshrined in the constitution, 2010.

KEYWORDS: Women, Social Justice, Bill Of Rights, Information Injustice.

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1. INTRODUCTION

International and regional deliberations on human rights have echoed and affirmed the right of access to information as a fundamental right. The genesis of this development began way back in the United Nations (1948) when a resolution was made to have the right of access to information be recognized as a primary human right. The culmination of that decree has been the inclusion of the right of access to information in human rights law and the Constitution which is considered the supreme law in many geographical jurisdictions (UNESCO, 2021). Moreover, both developed and developing countries have domesticated the right in their laws with Neuman (2022) indicating that over 130 countries have access to information laws. However, despite such efforts, Neuman (2022) still laments that women continue to suffer due to limited access to information. This is disturbing particularly when one considers developing countries like Kenya that have a myriad of challenges such as poverty, illiteracy, violence, backward traditional practices that hinder women from accessing information (Wyche & Oslon 2018; Neuman 2016).

Kenya made good its commitment to enact the Access to information Act (2016) following the passage of the Constitution (2010) that secured access to information a right under the bill of rights chapter. However, Kakah (2020) regrets that access to information is still an uphill struggle. This revelation is a stumbling block to the achievement of the vision 2030 (2007) under the political pillar that seeks among other strategies to inculcate a culture of compliance with laws by the year 2030. A culture of compliance with the laws can be successfully realized when people are acquainted with legal provisions of the laws governing their lives. One aspect of quality life is social justice which Sen (2014) posits that it serves to increase the capabilities of the marginalized so that they can do and be what they want. Moreover, social justice is one of the national values and principles of governance (Constitution, 2010) and

is the ultimate purpose for which the bill of rights chapter exists. Unfortunately, Koome (2023) cites lack of legal awareness as an impediment to social justice.

Matheka (2023) seems to burden women in Kenya with the responsibility of creating legal awareness when she warns that our society is in trouble if women don't teach their children justice matters. However, all is not lost following an insight by Marcella & Chowdhury (2019) that LIS professionals undertake social justice research as a means of addressing the needs of the marginalized and vulnerable populations. This article was launched from a social justice perspective in order to address the barriers that hinder women of Malava sub county from accessing and using legal information.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Oyelude & Bamighola (2012) posit that the state of not knowing is more devastating for a woman because she can easily transfer the ignorance to her offspring. When the state of not knowing legal information prevails, it is much more serious because the consequences of not living within the confines of the law implies more legal problems. Otiye (1996) and Ntombikayise (2018) decried the lack of access to legal information by the public where majority are women. People who have no clue of legal information affecting their lives are not able to know their entitlements and obligations embedded in laws. The result is that they continue to live in ignorance of the law which has serious legal implications (Mitee, 2017). Although legal information is heavily consumed by lawyers a study on Developmental information for rural women in Tanga, Tanzania by Mchombu (1994) revealed that rural women also required legal information. Study findings showed that 4.01% of the respondents interviewed expressed their interest have access to legal information. The reasons for requiring this kind of information were however not given and the number of respondents was also dismal suggesting that they lacked awareness on what legal information is and also where to find it. It is not enough for a country to pride in having legal information as observed by Neuman (2022) who is a champion of gender justice. She underscores that women's access to information must be a reality for the attainment of equity and equality to be realized. If justice is not only done but must be seen to be done then legal information should not only be available but rather, has to be accessed.

The common adage that information is power goes beyond availability of information. Meaningful decision making on matters such as education of their children, healthcare, agricultural production, active participation in public life among other concerns is hinged on accessible information yet Neuman (2016) decries that, women do not always have access to it. Following the serious decisions that have to be made on the basis of available and accessible information, the lack of it can impoverish a society. In a report on the state of poverty in devolved units of Kenya, KNBS (2020) cited peoples' access to information as one of the indicators it used in assessing the level of physical growth in devolved units of the country. This demonstrates the role that information plays in a region and Kenya having in place a framework on access to information implies that it attaches a lot of significance to information. Despite the presence of strong legislative frameworks in the recent past that have entrenched access to information as a fundamental human right, a study by the Carter Centre (2015) that sought to identify obstacles women in Liberia and Guatemala faced concluded that they were not able to exercise the right to information. Community leaders in these regions were asked to single out from a list of 18 potential barriers, the difficulties that women experienced in the course of looking for information. 87% of the community leaders cited lack of confidence by women to make a request as a large barrier. Other obstacles expressed by the community leaders included illiteracy; not knowing where to go/how to ask; issues of time and responsibilities and lack of mobility. As to what the expert respondents regarded as major obstacles to women exercising the right to information, the problems encountered included lack of education; prevalence of illiteracy; lack of awareness as well as cultural and traditional practices. These impediments made women's participation and voice to remain low. Culture was also cited as a hindrance to accessing legal information by rural women where respondents reported that they were not to question men and secondly not allowed to go back home. When information providers were interviewed, they averred that lack of equal rights, violence and abandonment were gender related problems that hindered women from access to information. Other challenges to accessing information by rural women that the respondents confessed to having included; lack of time due to heavy workload; lack of awareness; inadequate sources of information; customs and traditions; weak financial position of the majority of women which tended to lead to a lack of motivation to search for information.

A study by Wyche & Olson (2018) to assess rural women's realities with access to information and mobile phone usage rural women concluded the following;

- Internet access remains costly
- Women are confused about what it is
- Phones owned are likely not to have access to internet
- Overwhelming demands on rural women's time

Having phones is not enough to facilitate rural women access to legal information. While mobile penetration is high in the country there are challenges associated with its usage and so possession of mobiles should not be used to gauge access to the internet and information. The Global monitoring report for Education for all (2006) highlights the following as barriers that prevent women from

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accessing critical legal information: i) illiteracy ii) gender discrimination iii) paternalistic attitudes iv) social norms and v) discriminating interpretation of the law.

A worrying situation in the rural areas of Kenya which the World Bank (2011) revealed is that patriarchal traditions and community justice systems often override national legislation. This is a feature that is commonplace in majority areas of Kakamega where Ondiba(2020) revealed that its social system is not only patriarchal but tends to undermine women's way of life. It was felt by the researcher that the foregoing factors had a way of impacting negatively access to legal information by women and there was a need to establish the extent to which women were affected and also examine other barriers that existed.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The intention of this investigation was not to generalize from the sample but rather to describe and explain the barriers that hinder women from accessing legal information. This study was thus qualitative and the justification for this approach was that the subject of legal information has not been adequately addressed in the context of social justice with respect to women of Malava sub county, Kakamega. In the eyes of Creswell (2014) the use of qualitative research is highly recommended for a topic that has never been addressed on a particular group. The researcher felt that a qualitative orientation offered the benefit of understanding the breadth and depth of the identified phenomena because it centers on qualitative data collection which is also its backbone.

This section probed respondents on the challenges they felt barred them from accessing legal information which they had demonstrated they required to know about as it impacted on their lives. This finding corroborated an observation by Neuman (2016) who stated that women do not always have the benefit of accessing information yet they are the most in need of it.

4. FINDINGS

The following chapter reports the data findings that ensued from the field interviews with respondents. The respondents' own words are captured verbatim to demonstrate their lived experiences in as far as the phenomenon under study was investigated. When the rural women were asked to describe the barriers that hindered them from accessing legal information, they provided the following reasons,

i) Illiteracy: Low literacy status was decried by the respondents as a major stumbling block to their capacity in accessing and using legal information. A respondent quipped

'I really desire to know what the constitution says about me as a Kenyan, but I can't on my own, because I dropped school at class 5'

When the basic law is not known to an ordinary citizen, the rest of the laws will remain opaque yet it is within the natural law to know what is right and what is forbidden in one's jurisdiction of residence.

ii) Inadequate flow of information from the County Government: Devolution as a system of governance was preferred as a better mode of reaching the people believed to be unreached because of distance from the mainstream government headquarters that were located centrally in major towns or cities. I was tempted to assume that some legal information was within reach of women only for a respondent to express her disappointment at this when she went ahead to say the following:

"A lot of legal information is concentrated at the county headquarters making it impossible for the women to access since majority of them don't even know the location of the information."

The respondent seemed to be aware that it is the obligation of the county government to release legal information. From time immemorial locals understand that laws are granted by the government.

iii) Lack of time: Respondents noted that owing to their busy schedules that tie them to homes, farms and children they lacked time to attend to *barazas* where at times legal information was shared.

iv) Inadequate assistance from local leadership: Some respondents heaped blame on the local leadership and in particular Singled out village elders as not being available to assist them with some legal information. It was also noted that noted that some of the local leaders were not known to women because they rarely offered help. Moreover, another woman candidly stated that village elders were not available to create awareness. Local leadership is depended heavily by the rural population because they act as a bridge between the formal government and the people where they communicate government public information to their constituents. Apportioning blame on the local leadership was not over yet where a woman shared an experience that her friend went through. She had this to say:

Sometimes chiefs request to be facilitated in order to write letters introducing families to court in readiness to file succession cases. Close to this was a revelation by a woman who confessed to having been asked to pay for legal information. She said the following: I had a complaint against my neighbor who trespassed into my land and fell indigenous trees. When I went to the National Police service, I was asked to pay for copies of legal information that indicate penalties to pay in case one fells someone's trees.

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Making a similar comment, another respondent believed that legal information is availed on conditions when she said this “Legal information access sometimes is pegged on availability of money.

v) **Inferiority Complex:** Women have been described as vulnerable and marginalized groups that exist in our society. A number of factors have been attributed to this situation including low education levels, poverty, our patriarchal attitudes, backward cultures among other concerns. A respondent who appeared objective with her response stated this way:

Most women feel inferior such that they lack confidence to reach areas where they can get information

It is very unfortunate that conditions beyond the control of women made them feel afraid to an extent of not seeking information.

vi) **Lack of legal awareness:** A respondent stated that because of lack of awareness on the existence of legal information/laws, she could not benefit from the entitlements present in legal information. She suggested that with awareness she would be better placed to handle legal problems. Another stated the following.

Civic education is a right of every Kenyan, yet the government has failed to facilitate women access legal information.

Although inability to have access to smartphones was singled out by a respondent, the researcher went further to probe her how she could use a smartphone to access legal information. She stated that she could be able to access the internet with her children though not be in a position to locate legal information.

vii) **Attitude:** A Respondent noted that her search for legal information on boundary dispute on her land was met by a negative attitude from a local leader who felt she did not have a valid argument. She did not get assistance and had to seek help from another elder. According to her, she did not get a favorable response because her adversary had a blood relationship with the local leader. This is a very unfortunate situation where because of strained blood relationship a woman’s information need could not be filled.

5. DISCUSSIONS

Some of the activities that respondents stated they were involved in included health volunteering services and agricultural information volunteering services. Their assignment enabled the community to be aware of current developments and challenges in health and agriculture. This finding confirmed what Otiye (1996), Kiondo (1998) and Mchombu (1994) reported that agricultural information centres were set up in the majority of urban areas in the country and not legal resource institutions. The preamble of the access to information act sets out that every citizen has the right to access to information held by public and private institutions for the exercise of a right. Therefore, access to information should not be limited to agricultural information alone but ought to extend also to legal information.

One of the impediments highlighted by the respondents and which showed up during the interviews was fear where it was stated that women were engulfed with fear that strained them from freely requesting for legal information. Commenting on this barrier in a study that sought to identify obstacles that women in Guatemala and Liberia faced in accessing information, the Carter Center (2015) described lack of confidence to make a request as a larger barrier. Other obstacles reported in that study were expressed as grueling responsibilities, illiteracy, not knowing where to go to ask and lack of mobility. She later concluded that the impediments made women’s participation and voice to remain low. Furthermore, the Loomer report (2001) highlighted difficulties in communication concepts of rights in local languages and grueling responsibilities of women as the main blockade to women’s access to legal information.

6. CONCLUSION

This study concludes that the barriers women of Malava sub county face in securing legal information subject them to information injustice. This is contrary to the country’s principles of equity, human rights, equality and social justice as enshrined in the constitution, 2010. The principles essentially require that all citizens and in particular the marginalized are not excluded from services such as information.

7. IMPLICATIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The study established that women experienced barriers to accessing and using legal information. These included; illiteracy; inadequate flow of information from the county government; lack of time; inadequate assistance from local leadership; inferiority complex and lack of legal awareness. It can be inferred from the barriers that rural women of Malava sub county face that, they will remain ignorant of the law if the challenges they face are not addressed. Unfortunately, on the basis of the ancient legal principle that holds *ignorance of the law is no defense*, they cannot claim ignorance before a court of law or any an established government agency. Furthermore, they are likely to transfer their ignorance to their children according to Oyelude & Bamighola (2012) since it is undisputable that they are the caregivers of families, hence, spending a lot of time with children. In addition, Malava as a community is bound to get into trouble if the comments of Matheka(2023) are taken seriously where she warned that , if mothers don’t teach their children justice matters, our society has a problem.

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Based on the results of the empirical study, reviewed literature and conclusion of the study, the article provides the following policy and practical recommendations. It is recommended that County governments be deliberate in championing and facilitating the library services to create spaces that will ensure women have access legal information. The County of Kakamega is called upon to allocate more funds to the functions of the libraries in this regard. This study also calls upon the office of the woman representative to collaborate with women groups in the sub county of Malava with the objective of creating legal awareness to women. It is also necessary for the national government agencies, county governments, LSK and Civil society to partner in conducting civic education to both women and men on responsible citizenship following Matheka's (2023) counsel that children should be taught justice matters. Such an approach will ease the burden on women who are already overwhelmed with domestic chores. When women are enlightened, they will easily transfer knowledge to their children.

The national government through the Ministry of Interior and Coordination should ensure equal representation of women at local leadership roles and decision-making bodies. This will remove the fear of women visiting local administration offices to look for legal information Respondents had complained that owing to dominance of men in administrative positions they had fear of approaching the offices for help. This study recommends that the National Council of Law Reporting- NCLR sets up a desk in every *Huduma* centre in the country since this is a facility visited by majority of the public in search for public services. The desk should be manned by an officer from the agency who can offer legal information assistance.

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